

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE CONSTRUCTION OF A SUBJECT-SPATIAL DEVELOPING ENVIRONMENT IN THE SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE RESOURCES OF THE LOCAL COMMUNITY

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Abstract : the article presents achievements in the field of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the results of a national study on building a subject-spatial developing environment in a preschool educational organization, taking into account the resources of the local community.

Key words: subject-spatial developing environment, state curriculum " Ilk qadam ", local community resources.

In modern conditions, production, everyday life, forms of interaction between people require that a person, a child, not only general education, but, first of all, disclosure to an individual alnyh spocobnoctey, allowing you to achieve high results in work and make life more diverse.

Progressive reforms are being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at organizing an innovative system of preschool education, radically improving the system of preschool education, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing, taking into account the best international practices.

A clear confirmation of this is the increase in the coverage of children aged 3 to 7 years, if in 2017 it was 27%, then in 2023 it was 71.8%. Also in the country in accordance with the goals of sustainable development (SDG) task 4.2. obligatory free one-year preparation of children for school at the age of 6 years is provided, 90% are covered by this form.

At the government level, the Concept for the development of the system of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was adopted, where such priority tasks as creating conditions for all onnego intellectualogo, moralogo, aesthetic and physicalogo development of children doschoololnogo in ogogo, introduction into the system doschoololnogo the formation of innovations, advanced pedagogical and informational communication technologies.

As a result of the purposeful development of the system of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a opredeleno concept, the train "development of innovatsion elei of the subject-developing environment of doshkolnogo oeducation, ooptimization of coderzhatelnogo and protsessualnogo komponento in the succession of dosh kolnogo and obshchego nachalnogo obrazovaniya".

In 2018, the State Curriculum " Ilk qadam "(" First step ") for preschool educational organizations and in 2022, taking into account the study of the needs of teachers and existing experience, it was improved. This program is a new generation program, which was developed on a competency-based approach, where at the exit from the preschool educational

organization the child will have the following competencies: communicative, social, personal, cognitive.

A sociological survey conducted among 1,760 parents of preschool children showed that only 4% of parents are informed about the content of the subject-spatial developing environment, 69% expressed their willingness to cooperate with a preschool educational organization in modeling it.

According to numerous studies, it is the subject-spatial developmental environment that has the primary impact on the development of the child's personality, otherwise, as it will be seen a child will get the opportunity to develop their intellectual, creative abilities and successfully socialize in society.

At present, questions regarding the organization of a subject-spatial developing environment in the system of preschool education are the most in demand, since an important criterion for evaluating the activities of a school educational organization in cooperation with the State The new educational program "Ilk qadam" is the creation of a subject-spatial developing environment that meets modern requirements.

For preschool children, the developing environment cannot and should not be limited to a specific preschool educational organization. Because everything around us can and should act as an educational space that contributes not only to intellectual, but also to physical, aesthetic development.

At the same time, when organizing a subject-spatial developing environment in a preschool educational organization, as the study showed, insufficient attention is paid to the use of local resources.

In November 2022, in Tashkent, ministers, heads and members of delegations, representatives of United Nations (UN) agencies, development cooperation organizations, civil society organizations, specialists and experts in the field of education, at the invitation of the Director-General of UNESCO, gathered in the city Tashkent (Uzbekistan) to participate in the World Conference on Early Childhood Care and Education, where, as a result, the Tashkent Declaration was adopted, which defines the main and joint commitments to transform the system of early childhood education and upbringing until 2030.

One of the directions for the implementation of the Tashkent Declaration is the task "Variety of learning spaces, practices and provision of early childhood care and education" (ECCE).

This target stipulates that all children should have the opportunity to learn in preschool educational institutions and beyond, including in households, communities, playgrounds, museums, libraries and other places. Children in marginalized or vulnerable situations, such as those living in poverty, in remote or rural areas, indigenous and nomadic children, children with disabilities or those affected by crises, may need tailored quality ECCE models that are more appropriate for their specific needs, conditions and needs.

The huge developing potential of the nearest whirling of the child should be recognized and realized by teachers. Resources of the local society - natural, historical-architectural, cultural-obrassive and other material and spiritual benefits must be used in a long measure with the aim of developing the personality of the child. Knowledge of the resources of the teachers in the local society and their use for the organization of the educational process - in the nipple to bring them closer to the interests and needs of children of preschool age, to

create prerequisites for the establishment and strengthening of civil society, for the development of local communities .

The local community where the child lives is a powerful resource that affects the development of the child's personality. There are many niya. Children can attend activities such as plays, music and dance activities, as well as watch street performers and workers doing different jobs. They can visit various parks, squares, organizations where children are engaged, sports and music sections, elementary school, hospital. They can go on walks for various purposes, such as recording different views of doors, windows, yards, etc. to link to items or projects in a group.

Also an important aspect is the involvement of parents in strengthening the educational environment in a family environment. Educators can help families improve their children's learning by offering them activities and materials to use at home or in the community. These activities may include language and literacy classes that family members may take with the children. These may include books to read together, interactive magazines, culinary activities, and various things that children may not do in a park or playground, or observe in nature. If the children are studying a specific topic in a group, they can interview family members about that topic, draw pictures together, make up stories, and write them down together.

In this way, the attention of a teacher can be focused on things that make the surrounding world of children - different, filled with their personal o torture and having for each of them personal, personal, personal meaning; understanding and attention is not simply adapting to the environment, but also "getting used to" children in it, namely, at its own level, give the child the opportunity to explore, constructively and couse available resources, positively transform, only with such a fodhode will be obecopecheno mutualoe cocooperationo with local communities and in the attraction of parents and their families in the educational process.

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